

COMMUNICATION AS THERAPY

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Abstract

The present study is located on the perimeter of communication as science. It focuses on the study of a special type of communication: communication as therapy, communication as a delicate intervention in the imaginary and in the current reality. The method used is a case study type. The case of therapy through literary-poetic communication is investigated. The conclusion reached is that through lyrical communication a change is produced in the real plane. Lyrical speech is a second kind of speech in relation to the psychological speech centered on therapy. Both speeches are communicative interventions. If the secondary, derived discourse has a therapeutic effect, then it follows that the primary discourse has a therapeutic effect and that the therapeutic tool is communication.

Keywords: communication, therapy, therapeutic effect, communication as therapy

1. What is happening to us

"When the earth will spin around me" (Editura Colorama, Cluj-Napoca, 2023) by Aurora Popescu is a book written with talent, which helps us see better what is happening to us, although it seems that it is not happening in the right way essentially nothing. It contains poems developed over 30 years and represents a remarkable poetic debut.

Aurora Popescu discovers poetry as self-therapy and putting things in order. He does not write simply to express himself, but above all to express others, to express the world. Take on what oppresses them, what stresses them, what overwhelms them or what tyrannizes others. Then he meditatively sublimates the pressures of the world into poetry as a therapy for his pressures. It is the poetry of a liberator from others and from himself. His lyrics are an elegant, delicate, graceful and intricate mirror through which things are set. Everyone's states, situations, anxieties and inquiries are reflected in this mirror. Not everyone finds or

invents the language of such a mirror. In the mirror is the life of the poet, of each of us, of us, of the world, of the cosmos. In the mirror, everyone sees what they are able to see and experience, feel. Beyond this metaphor, Aurora Popescu's lyrics are a discourse of moments, moments and lyrical vibrations.

We all experience moments of poetry, epic moments, tragic moments throughout our existence. Aurora Popescu has her moments of real or imaginary poetry, irradiated by others or by herself. His poems are more than those moments, they are like lyrical charge over those magical seconds with taste and vibe of eternity. The quality that Aurora Popescu has to metamorphose, to sublimate life or imagination into beauty is called talent.

The poet writes as if the future is coming undeservedly and unfairly faster towards us. We had a certain rhythm and it seemed like we were going to catch the end of the world. With acceleration we find that only our end is given to us and we certainly catch it. Suddenly it seems that the future is upon us. Leave fear and haste; these are nothing but the fact that the present turns too quickly into the past, the past becomes memory and oblivion, and we see ourselves as earth.

The first sensation is a tonic one: here the earth will revolve around me, we are the sun of our social system. That's right, it just surrounds us and leaves us with no way out.

2. Structuring

The volume of 67 poems is relevantly prefaced by Gela Enea. is dedicated by the poet to her mother and opens with three poems about the mother's omnipresence ("Mother with a thousand hands", "Letter", "That day when the earth will revolve around me": "my mother's hands/ will take my cold "). Then it appears in several poems, such as: "Rebirth" ("I should forget that you died/ (...) / you made me/ my mother"), "Her name" ("I think my mother didn't read any poetry"), "Scaiete", "Solstition". 7 of the 67 poems in the volume are directly or incidentally connected to the mother. It can be said that the main theme and the thought that radiates throughout the volume, according to the dedication, is the mother.

The second major theme of the book is time; this mobilizes the meaning of 25 poems. We can talk about several forms of time. First,

time is recollection: "I remember (...)/ (...)/ time stood still/ (...)/ I see my mother/ reading (...) my letter" ("Letter"). Time warps "time bends under us" ("Promises"). One form is the time after when there will be time for everything: "I park more and more poorly/ and forget more and more often where/ I cram some memories/ peace teas/ some expensive anti-wrinkle creams/ insomnia pills/ the protective factor/ and the pink shoes/ one day I'll have time for everything" ("State of Grace"). Time appears as seasons, spring, autumn, winter; for example, autumn brings unhappiness to trees "Crosses on graves/ (...) leaves" ("Autumn"). An interesting form of duration is inverse time: "the dice were wasted/ in my destiny/ (...)/ time/ chose to flow in reverse/ one day I will end up alone/ by myself" ("Inverse "). Time puts us under pressure and life runs, "age runs" ("Fear"). The passage of years makes man a victim of time, a delayed being: "soon we will learn to be victims/ (...)/ the lateness has begun" ("Too late"). We encounter the time when man prepares to die: "more and more alone/ we prepare to leave without being prepared/ (...)/ let's go to the future" ("Lessons from the Future"). Man is a victim of time; this is the time of exiting the scene: "I still miss the end/ it's still hard for me/ to witness/ dying" ("Victim"); the trees are the "morning/ of a coffin" ("***"). We also have a poem of the time after us, beyond death: "we no longer exist/ on the radio it is announced/ that the Big Bang theory/ was a lie" ("The Lie").

A theme that polarizes the interest of 9 poems is love. We have lost love ("We", "Partaj": "never understood/ who wins/ when we both lose"), resigned love ("You"), sacrificial love ("Love"), coffee-flavored love bitter ("Taste"), love as a cage ("Another cage"), love as capital punishment ("Knife", "poetry is a knife with a long blade / that stabs us both"), consumed love ("Tenderness"), compelling love ("Points") and changed love ("Relationship": "from single/ to a complicated relationship").

The fourth theme that permeates the volume is the theme of the poetic self and the theme of poetics or poetic art. The speech of the poem is a memory affected by Alzheimer's, imperfectly written with the left hand that only brings a deficient self-discovery: "I write with my left/ at the edge of time/ (...) / the way home/ is Alzheimer's" ("Alzheimer"). The lyrical self, specializing in lost causes ["lost causes are my specialty" ("Story)], wanders without knowing "what time it is" ("Disorientation"),

trying in vain to "turn back the clock" ("Inhabited Winter"). He lives in a place where "nothing ever happens" ("****"), where he sees "hand made smiles". It is not found "in this world of zig-zags" ("Zig-zag"). Here he writes his "thoughts under the pulse of the moment" ("Send"), with no spare time. because "it's been getting evening for a while" ("Her name"). Write because there is no more time; "I don't have time to postpone anything" ("Now"). He writes for not forgetting, for remembering: "I'm afraid not to forget that I was here/ (...)/ under the hungry thighs of time/ (...)/ the grains of remembering" ("Darkness"). The lyrical self huddles "between the clay covers/ of the passage" ("A death, a smile and a poem"). The signature poem of the book is "A death, a smile and a poem". Grave lyrical meditation on death becomes poem under the guise of a smile. Death smiles at us from poems.

We are dealing with a remarkable positioning, with a book written with talent and whose great poems are at the end: "Too late", "State of grace", "Inverse", "Zig-zag", "On the peaks", "From the seasons", "Memory of maps", "Close to the truth".

3. Conclusion

Lyrical speech uses elements of psychological discourse and has therapeutic effects. It remains to be researched whether an emphasis on psychological therapeutic elements preserves the therapeutic effects in the lyrical register or takes them to a purely psychological register.

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